

Assessing the FAIRness of databases on the EHDEN portal: A case study on two Dutch ICU databases

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To address the growing need for effective data reuse in health research, healthcare institutions need to make their data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). A prevailing method to model databases for interoperability is the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM), developed by the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) initiative. A European repository for OMOP CDM-converted databases called the “European Health Data & Evidence Network (EHDEN) portal” was developed, aiming to make these databases Findable and Accessible. This paper aims to assess the FAIRness of databases on the EHDEN portal.

Materials and methods: Two researchers involved in the OMOP CDM conversion of separate Dutch Intensive Care Unit (ICU) research databases each manually assessed their own database using seventeen metrics. These were defined by the FAIRsFAIR project as a list of minimum requirements for a database to be FAIR. Each metric is given a score from zero to four based on how well the database adheres to the metric. The maximum score for each metric varies from one to four based on the importance of the metric.

Results: Fourteen out of the seventeen metrics were unanimously rated: seven were rated the highest score, one was rated half of the highest score, and five were rated the lowest score. The remaining three metrics were assessed differently for the two use cases. The total scores achieved were 15.5 and 12 out of a maximum of 25.

Conclusion: The main omissions in supporting FAIRness were the lack of globally unique identifiers such as Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) in the OMOP CDM and the lack of metadata standardization and linkage in the EHDEN portal. By implementing these in future updates, the EHDEN portal can be more FAIR.

1. Introduction

Analytics, big data, and artificial intelligence have played a significant role in the development of health care in the twenty-first century, improving the efficiency, quality, and safety of care [1–4]. Although these advancements have been supported by an increasing amount of digital health data and more powerful computer systems, more progress could be made if health data were standardized and accessible for analysis.

In 2016, Wilkinson et al. [5] proposed four foundational principles to facilitate effective data reuse. Research data should be stored in a way that ensures its Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and

Reusability (FAIR). Study data should be easily found (F) online so researchers can easily increase the size of their cohorts. This data should somehow be accessible (A) to anyone who finds it, though it may incorporate authentication and authorization procedures. When obtained, the data should be unambiguously understood and merged with other data, hence interoperable (I), with a minimum of technical work or harmonization. Lastly, data should be described with rich metadata. This means that not only should the meaning and context of data be made clear with detailed descriptions, but also the provenance and usage license. Data reusability (R) hinges on this rich metadata, together with databases following community standards that meet the other three FAIR principles.

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Despite widespread acclaim, implementation of these principles remains challenging [6–8]. Researchers have tried to put the FAIR principles into practice by implementing well-established data storage and exchange standards [9–12]. One of these standards is developed by OHDSI [13], a collaborative aiming to standardize medical databases with their database model, the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Database Model (CDM) [14]. The OMOP data model defines a patient-based data structure using a predefined collection of standardized vocabularies [15] which describes the data. This level of standardization makes it easy to share both the data and its precise meaning [16], which should support the ‘I’ of FAIR.

With the goal of accelerating real-world health research, the European Health Data Evidence Network (EHDEN) project is currently assisting healthcare institutions throughout Europe with standardizing their databases with the OMOP CDM [17]. To create a community of health care researchers, they also provide an infrastructure to publish European healthcare databases converted to the OMOP CDM called the EHDEN portal. On its website, EHDEN-affiliated researchers can find data using the metadata on the EHDEN portal, and apply for data reuse, supporting the ‘F’, ‘A’, and ‘R’ of FAIR.

Together, the OMOP CDM and the EHDEN portal aim to contribute to the implementation of a FAIR research repository, facilitating proper reuse of medical data for research purposes. However, the FAIRness of the included databases has not been assessed yet. This study therefore aims to assess the FAIRness of databases on the EHDEN portal using two case studies from the portal: a national intensive care quality registry database and a COVID-19 ICU research database. With this orientation, goals for future improvements can be brought to light to make the databases in the EHDEN portal more FAIR.

2. Methods

2.1. Databases

The FAIRness of databases transformed to the OMOP CDM and published on the EHDEN portal was evaluated and illustrated with two use cases. These databases were chosen because of the authors’ familiarity with them. Both were part of studies in which the source databases were

transformed to the OMOP CDM by the authors DP and RG. The authors then published the databases on the EHDEN portal after filling in the necessary metadata. This includes the results from the R package “CatalogueExport”, which was made by EHDEN to summarize the data through graphs. To expand on the previous studies and enhance the generalizability of the results, the two databases were both assessed in this study.

The first use case was the database of the Dutch National Intensive Care Evaluation (NICE). Started in 1996 and primarily used for quality improvement and research purposes, it contains over 1.3 million records of ICU admissions. With over 400 data elements on patient demographics, physiological features, and comorbidities, it describes the severity of illness as well as hospital and ICU mortality and length of stay for all critically ill patients admitted to one of the 80 Dutch intensive care units (ICU). For this study, we used a subset of this data, the minimal dataset (MDS). It includes, for example, the length of stay, diagnosis, Glasgow Coma Scale, discharge destination, physiological measurements, and laboratory test results. All 80 ICUs are required to submit data to the MDS, which now contains 1.3 million records and 104 data items. The definitions of all data items can be found on the website of the NICE, which contains a data dictionary [18].

The second use case was the Dutch ICU Data Warehouse for COVID-19 (DIDWC19) which was launched at the start of the COVID-19 pandemic in March 2020. It contains 942 data elements on demographics, clinical observations, device data, medication, and laboratory data of 1800 COVID-19 patients, extracted from the EHRs of 25 Dutch ICUs. Example data items are ICU mortality, bronchial suctioning, mechanical ventilator settings, oral medications, and blood gas analyses. It does not have a public website or data dictionary [19].

2.2. Extract transform and load (ETL) process

Both use cases underwent preprocessing; an extract, transform, and load (ETL) operation to conform the data structure to the OMOP CDM; validation of data quality through the use of EHDEN and OMOP CDM tooling; and publication on the EHDEN portal (see Fig. 1 [6]). This process is defined by OHDSI, and the results were validated by EHDEN. The resulting OMOP CDM conforming database was then published on the EHDEN portal [20–21].

Fig. 1. A flowchart of the process from the NICE registry database to the OMOP CDM database. The tools used are mentioned in parentheses. All tools except the Microsoft Structured Query Language server (MSSQL) [22] have been developed by OHDSI [6].

2.3. FAIRsFAIR data Object assessment metrics

To properly assess the FAIRness of the databases on the EHDEN portal, we could not directly use the FAIR principles, as these were deliberately kept vague to account for all use cases and domains. Moreover, Wilkinson et al. [5,23–24] repeatedly specified that they were never intended as strict definitions of their subject but rather loose guidelines or goals to aim for. We therefore needed a tool that assessed each FAIR principle in as much detail as possible and was applicable to health research databases such as our use cases.

Available to assess the FAIRness of a dataset are a multitude of (semi-)automated tools and manual metric surveys [23,25–26]. Notable ones were outlined in a recent study by Krans et al. [25]. They concluded that the FAIR evaluator software [23] was the most promising automated tool, and SATIFYD [26] was the most promising survey. However, the FAIR evaluator software can only be run on databases openly accessible online. Due to security and privacy considerations, medical research databases like our use cases are only accessible through the internet after extensive authorization processes.

The SATIFYD survey was not comprehensive enough for our study. To quote its own introduction: “The 12 questions touch upon the FAIR data principles but do not strictly follow them.” [26]. We also found the questions were focused on integrating databases into their own data repository, such as asking for preferred formats. The answers were also restricted to simplifications rather than detailed justifications, such as “Rich metadata with as much information as possible”. Therefore, the FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics (henceforth FAIRsFAIR metrics) were chosen for our study [27]. These are seventeen well-described metrics to assess the adherence to the FAIR principles and are based on the FAIR indicators from the FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group [28]. The FAIRsFAIR metrics focus on the minimum requirements for a database to be FAIR. As opposed to SATIFYD, the FAIRsFAIR metrics closely follow the FAIR principles and allow for detailed explanations on the adherence to the metrics. We used version 0.5 (March 8, 2022) [27].

2.4. Evaluation procedure

The evaluation required knowledge of the structure, data, and metadata of the source database as well as knowledge on the specific implementation of the ETL from the source database to the OMOP CDM. As each researcher was deeply involved in the ETL of their respective databases, it was determined to be valuable to have the seventeen metrics independently applied to the NICE database on EHDEN portal by researcher DP and to the DIDWC19 on EHDEN portal by researcher RG.

For each metric, a maturity level was assigned to a database, ranging from zero to three, based on requirements specified in the FAIRsFAIR report [27]. The maturity level determines the score given, which varies per metric. This means that sometimes a maturity level one means one point, and sometimes it means half a point, depending on the weight of the metric. The total achieved score shows the current FAIRness of the database on the EHDEN portal, with 0 out of 25 being not FAIR and 25 out of 25 being completely FAIR. Comments were provided by both researchers to support the assessments. Importantly, these assessments were conducted independently of the other researcher. Afterward, the answers of both researchers per metric were compared to determine how FAIR the OMOP CDM databases on the EHDEN portal were. Any discrepancies were discussed with an expert team of medical informaticians with extensive knowledge of the two datasets and the FAIR principles (authors FBR, RC, NdK). The assessments were adjusted as necessary after the insights gained during this discussion.

3. Results

Table 1 shows the seventeen metrics with their assessments and comments. Fourteen out of the seventeen metrics were given the same

score by both researchers: eight were rated the highest score and five were rated the lowest score. The metrics with the lowest score are:

- FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.
- FsF-F3-01 M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.
- FsF-F4-01 M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.
- FsF-I1-01 M - Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.
- FsF-R1.3-01 M - Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research

community of the data.

These lowest-scoring metrics highlight the need to integrate globally unique, persistent identifiers in the OMOP CDM and use them in the EHDEN portal. Metadata on the EHDEN portal should also be transformed to a metadata standard and represented in a knowledge language. By using these, databases can be found and accessed better through, for example, popular search engines such as Google or Bing.

The assessment of the remaining three metrics was different for the two use cases:

- FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.
- FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.
- FsF-R1.1-01 M - Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.

The first metric mentioned shows the need for better instructions for making an ETL to the OMOP CDM. The other two both mention the NICE data dictionary as an extra source of metadata, which can be accessed on the EHDEN portal through a link. The NICE data dictionary contains metadata describing exactly how the data was recorded at the source, and all properties it has in the database itself. This underlines the difference it makes to have a metadata repository detailing the exact context and properties of the data.

NICE achieved a total score of 15.5 out of 25 and DIDWC19 a total score of 12 out of 25.

4. Discussion

We assessed the FAIRness of two ICU OMOP CDM databases on the EHDEN portal by measuring the minimum requirements of FAIRness. This assessment shows that the two databases on the EHDEN portal were not considered completely FAIR, as both the OMOP CDM and the EHDEN portal still have room for improvement to further optimize data reuse.

The most important gaps found are the ones where the researchers unanimously agreed that the metrics did not satisfy either use case, scoring zero for both. Firstly, the OMOP CDM does not include URIs as IDs and is thus not able to properly link the data. This issue makes the EHDEN portal unable to refer to the data in a machine-readable way. Another gap was that the EHDEN portal does not define its metadata using a formal knowledge representation language such as RDF [36], nor does it structure it using a metadata standard such as DCAT [37] or Dublin Core [34]. Implementing these would allow metadata on the EHDEN portal to have qualified references to and relationships with related data and metadata. It would also make the EHDEN portal interoperable with other health institutes, such as the European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases, which also uses DCAT and RDF to standardize their metadata [38–39].

Interestingly, mapping databases with similar ICU data to the OMOP CDM and publishing it on the EHDEN portal should result in similar levels of FAIRness, yet the researchers still found dissimilarities. The Findability and Reusability metrics had different assessments where the metric was fully implemented in one dataset but not in the other. A reason for the difference in Findability (FsF-F1-02D) was due to a

Table 1

The FAIRsFAIR metrics, and assessments on both NICE and the DDW datasets on EHDEN portal. The assessments are defined in scores based on FAIR maturity levels [27], independently given to the NICE by researcher DP and to the DIDWC19 by researcher RG. Since the scores vary per metric, we note them as follows: score given/maximum score. In additional comments, both researchers state the reasons for their scores. The column 'Comment DIDWC19' displays "Similar assessment" when both researchers assessed a metric with the same score and same reason for their data source.

Metrics	Score NICE	Score DIDWC19	Comment NICE	Comment DIDWC19
FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.	0/1	0/1	The database has data identifiers, a simple series of numbers that could also be used in other databases and are therefore not globally unique. The metadata within the database uses ATHENA [15], the OHDSI database of medical terminologies, which does have globally unique concept identifiers.	Similar assessment.
FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.	0.5/1	0/1	Data identifiers persist if the database does. When adding data, we assigned each record a number that was one higher than the previous number. By not linking this with the automatic index order number in the table, the identifiers remain persistent. However, it is not a resolvable Uniform Resource Locator (URL). The database is described on the EHDEN portal [29]. Descriptive core elements are available, as well as a statistical summary of the data generated by the DataCatalogueExport R package.	The data identifiers are linked to the automatic index number. Because of this, updates could affect the identifiers.
FsF-F2-01 M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.	2/2	2/2	The metadata on the EHDEN portal does not include an identifier of the data it describes. Thus, the data cannot be discovered through its metadata.	Similar assessment.
FsF-F3-01 M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.	0/1	0/1	The metadata on the EHDEN portal is not registered in major research data registries like DataCite and is not given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogs, like in JSON-LD, Dublin Core or RDFa.	Similar assessment.
FsF-F4-01 M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.	0/2	0/2	The metadata has a place to add a description of the ethical and governance approval process. This also includes a document detailing the procedure.	Similar assessment.
FsF-A1-01 M - Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.	1/1	1/1	Metadata on the data and the database is retrievable via the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) on the EHDEN portal [29].	Similar assessment.
FsF-A1-02 M - Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol	1/1	1/1	Due to security reasons, data is not directly accessible through standardized communication protocols such as HTTP. However, through a specialized protocol, data can be visited via ATLAS, an OHDSI data analysis application.	Similar assessment.
FsF-A1-03D - Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.	1/1	1/1	When the data is unavailable, the metadata is still available. The EHDEN portal includes a dashboard with all metadata and visualized data, created with OHDSI's DataCatalogueExport R package.	Similar assessment.
FsF-A2-01 M - Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available.	1/1	1/1	Metadata is represented using free text and can be exported to a CSV file; neither are formal knowledge representation languages. There is no parsable structured metadata or graph data available in, for example, JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data (JSON-LD) or Resource Description Framework (RDF) format.	Similar assessment.
FsF-I1-01 M - Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.	0/2	0/2	Part of the data is codified with metadata through standardized terminologies in the OMOP vocabulary. SNOMED-CT and LOINC [16] were used. The data elements that were not codified received a custom NICE code to fully contain the correct meaning.	The data is codified with standardized terminologies in the OMOP vocabulary. SNOMED-CT [30], RxNorm [31], and LOINC [16] were used.
FsF-I2-01 M - Metadata uses semantic resources	1/1	1/1	The EHDEN portal includes links to other metadata on the data, such as publications, documents, and websites. However, that is the extent of the linkage between the data and its related entities. This can be expanded with metadata on funding and organizations, among other things. Furthermore, there is no possibility to link metadata on the EHDEN portal using unique identifiers.	Similar assessment.
FsF-I3-01 M - Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.	1/1	1/1	The metadata on the EHDEN portal links to the NICE website, which contains the NICE data dictionary. It describes in detail what the data is, the data format, and how the data is gathered by healthcare professionals in the context of the ICU [32]. The described data is verifiable in the database. However, the file type, size, and other technical data descriptors are not available.	The summary on the EHDEN portal gives minimal information about the concepts used, which can be verified in the database. There are no data descriptors for technical specifics or the context of the observed data points.
FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.	3/4	2/4	The metadata on the EHDEN portal links to the NICE website, which has a copyright section clearly stating the terms of usage of the data, verifiable by Dutch law [33].	The EHDEN portal does not have license information available.
FsF-R1.1-01 M - Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.	2/2	0/2		

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Metrics	Score NICE	Score DIDWC19	Comment NICE	Comment DIDWC19
FsF-R1.2-01 M - Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.	1/2	1/2	The provenance of the data is described in the metadata in the database and on the EHDEN portal [14,29], but it is not described using provenance ontologies such as PROV-O.	Similar assessment.
FsF-R1.3-01 M - Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.	0/1	0/1	Standards such as DublinCore [34] or the Metadata Object Description Schema (MODS) [35] were not used to structure or define the metadata.	Similar assessment.
FsF-R1.3-02D - Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.	1/1	1/1	The OMOP CDM and EHDEN portal are part of the OHDSI community of researchers, who all use the same database structure and set of vocabularies [14].	Similar assessment.
Total Achieved Score	15.5/25	12/25		

difference in the implementation of data identifiers within the underlying database infrastructure: one linked the record IDs to their table index, while the other did not. The former reduces the persistence of the records by allowing table updates to alter their IDs. A reason for the difference in Reusability (FsF-R1-01MD, FsF-R1.1-01 M) was the EHDEN portal linking to the NICE website. It contains license information and specifies data definitions, while this type of rich metadata is unavailable for the other dataset. Such metadata plays a crucial role in understanding the database, which begs the question of whether OHDSI and EHDEN should integrate these elements of FAIRness into, respectively, the OMOP CDM and the EHDEN portal.

This study was limited by the small number of included use cases and the overlap in their content. Both used Dutch ICU data, potentially limiting the generalizability of the results to other medical contexts. Databases in other domains may use the OMOP CDM differently due to differences in content. However, the use of two similar use cases demonstrated that within similar datasets, the assessment of the FAIRsFAIR metrics may still deviate due to choices in the ETL to the OMOP CDM and the availability of a data dictionary outside of the EHDEN portal. Another limitation was that only two researchers assessed the use cases. Having multiple assessors might result in a more rigorous FAIR assessment, as they could have discovered different results unnoticed by the other assessors.

A strength of this study is that it is the first study on the FAIRness of datasets on the EHDEN portal, a successful international initiative with over 87 datasets published on the portal. Though the topic “FAIRness” was discussed in the OHDSI community in 2020, no further developments were explicitly noted afterward. This study may reinvigorate this discussion within and outside the OHDSI community, as well as highlight areas for improvement. Another strength is that the FAIRness of data models, supporting tools, and data portals is often not explored, though they all aim to improve interoperability by standardizing the way data is structured. Moreover, the OMOP CDM goes beyond that, requiring data elements to be codified using standardized vocabularies. How this affects the FAIRness of the data model was previously unknown, but with this assessment we confirmed that it does improve, making their requirement a worthwhile investment. Lastly, in light of the upcoming European Open Science Cloud, the FAIRsFAIR project aims to be the platform where European researchers go to for guidance on the FAIR principles [40]. The FAIRsFAIR metrics would then be the primary way to assess the FAIRness of databases. This makes this paper especially relevant, as the same metrics we used will most likely be used in the future by European researchers assessing the FAIRness of their research data.

From our assessment, we can conclude that OMOP CDM on the EHDEN portal does not guarantee fully FAIR implementations, insofar as the minimal requirements are concerned. Future developments should focus on the integration of globally unique, persistent identifiers; metadata schemas and description languages; and space for clear usage licenses and data element descriptions. Specifically, data and metadata should use globally unique identifiers to specify specific data or

metadata. By doing this, the EHDEN portal can have more outreach and can link with other medical research repositories due to its increased findability. Furthermore, clarity should be introduced by having a space on the EHDEN portal to describe the usage license of a resource and the data elements in that resource. This information is useful for researchers wanting details on the data they would like to use for their research. Lastly, the EHDEN portal is still under development, and the OMOP CDM is rapidly improving based on community feedback. Therefore, a follow-up to this study should be conducted to monitor the FAIRness of OMOP CDM databases on the EHDEN portal.

Summary Table

What was already known on the topic	What this study added to our knowledge
FAIR data principles are an important aspect of research data management but can be difficult to implement.	This study shows a concrete way to assess a FAIR implementation.
The OMOP CDM increases interoperability of observational health data, and the EHDEN portal facilitates Findability and Accessibility. These together should increase the Reusability of observational health data.	We now know exactly how FAIR OMOP CDM and EHDEN portal are by measuring them against the FAIRsFAIR metrics.
	The OMOP CDM databases on the EHDEN portal are good ways to increase FAIRness, but they still have flaws that need to be amended.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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